

Analysis of the Effect of Development of Hospital Management Information System Based on Knowledge Management on Employee Performance of Dr Wahidin Sudirohusodo, Makassar

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to (1) find out the relationship between knowledge management hospital management information system development on employee performance, (2) analyze the influence of knowledge management hospital management information system development on employee performance, (3) analyze the partial influence of home management information system development knowledge management based pain towards employee performance. The study uses quantitative methods with explanatory correlational designs. Sampling is done by purposive sampling method with a sample size of 94 people. Data were analyzed using Yates Correction Test and Multiple Regression. The results of the study show that there is a relationship between the development of knowledge management SIMRS and employee performance. There is the influence of the development of knowledge management SIMRS on employee performance. Only 2 of the 4 knowledge management SIMRS development variables have a partial effect on employee performance, namely Knowledge Transfer and Knowledge Application.

Keywords: Knowledge Management Process, SIMRS, Employee Performance

INTRODUCTION

Today the development of organizations in all sectors is increasingly leading to intense competition, competition in the form of services, ease of systems and product excellence continues to force every organization to make improvements and

improvements. Knowledge is considered to be an important weapon in achieving and maintaining an organization's competitive advantage (Rastogi 2000; Senge 2000). Knowledge has a very important role in the progress of a company / organization. Many companies increasingly recognize the importance of knowledge as one of the capital to achieve competitive advantage. The more advanced knowledge the company has, the higher the company's competitiveness. Knowledge creation in an organization cannot be done instantly, but it requires processes and enabler factors (supporting factors to make it happen). The stages of creating knowledge in organizations in the context of the application of knowledge management begin with enablers factors that will trigger a knowledge management process, which then results in organizational creativity, which in turn will have an impact on organizational performance (Lee & Choi, 2003). Available electronic resources are the first target for information seekers, faced with new challenges to provide relevant and timely information and come from many sources. In other words it is challenged to provide the entire spectrum of information, not only limited to explicit knowledge, so it is necessary to explore the concept of applying Knowledge Management in the work environment, including hospitals which are a very important part of a health system.

If the Information System is implemented well in the context of the Hospital, it will change the health care system over the next few decades to be more cost effective, prevent errors, and measurable public resources. Carl Davidson and Philip Voss (2003) say that actually managing knowledge is the way organizations manage their employees, and how long they spend on information technology. The existence of the Hospital Information System (SIRS) implemented by Dr. Wahidin Sudirohusodo Hospital has made the importance of knowledge continuously explored, processed, managed and developed continuously using information technology so that data, information and knowledge are more easily displayed and communicated and become a place for sharing between parts / unit within the Hospital. Moreover, with the Regulation of the State Minister for Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform Number 14 of 2011 concerning Guidelines for Implementing Knowledge Management Programs that expect Ministries / Agencies and Regional Governments to actively participate in the implementation of Knowledge Management that can be utilized in policy formulation and benchmarking for the implementation of bureaucratic reform.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Location and Design of Research

The study was conducted for 1 (one) month, namely the first Sunday of July 2014 to the third week of July 2014 was held at RSUP Dr. Wahidin Sudirohusodo Makassar.

Population and Samples

The population is all employees of RSUP Dr. Wahidin Sudirohusodo Makassar totaling 1,580 employees. The research sample amounted to 94 employees.

Method of collecting data

Primary data: data obtained by researchers for specific purposes in answering research problems (Malhotra, 2000). Primary data collection in this study was carried out

through the distribution of questionnaires prepared to all respondents.

Secondary Data: data collected for specific purposes other than research problems (Malhotra, 2000). Secondary data in the form of Profiles and Annual Reports and Performance Reports of Dr Wahidin Sudirohusodo Hospital Makassar.

Data analysis method

The method of data analysis in this study is descriptive statistics, namely the frequency distribution of measurement results of research variables and analytical statistics, namely the method of analyzing collective and separate contributions of two or more independent variables on variations in the dependent variable [Kerlinger and Pedhazur, 1973].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Univariate analysis in this study was conducted on categorizing variables on respondents' answers regarding Knowledge Creation, Knowledge Storage / Retrieval, Knowledge Transfer and Knowledge Application, Development of RS Management Information Systems and Employee Performance. From the results of the univariate analysis, it was found that 94.7% of respondents thought Knowledge Creation was good as part of the Knowledge Management Process in the development of information systems even though there were still 5.3% of respondents who argued that Knowledge Creation was not good, this was confirmed by Mohanta, 2006 which states that some things that can improve performance are with Information Technology and Knowledge Management where of course there is a process of knowledge creation that is expected to continue to take place.

From the results of the univariate analysis it was found that 93.6% of respondents thought that Knowledge Storage was good as part of the Knowledge Management Process in developing information systems even though there were still 6.4% of respondents who thought Knowledge Storage was still not good,

knowledge storage and retrieval was very important in the development and refinement of a hospital SIM. The majority of Knowledge Transfer held by Respondents is in the Good category as part of the Knowledge Management Process in the development of information systems as many as 89 employees or as much as 94.7% while the respondents who are in the Poor category are only 5 employees or 5.3% of the total respondents.

The majority of knowledge applications owned by respondents are in the Good category as many as 91 employees or equal to 96.8% while the respondents who are in the category of Poor are only 3 employees or 3.2% of the total respondents. The development of the Hospital Management Information System owned by the majority of respondents is in the Good category as many as 88 employees or as much as 93.6% while the respondents who are in the Poor category are only 6 employees or 6.4% of the total respondents.

The majority of Employee Performance held by Respondents is in the Good category, as many as 87 employees or 92.6% while the respondents who are in the Poor category are only 7 employees or 7.4% of the total respondents. Bivariate analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between independent variables Knowledge Management Development of RS-based SIM with the dependent variable Employee Performance at Dr. RSUP Wahidin Sudirohusodo Makassar by conducting cross tabulations and statistical analysis using Chi Square by using a degree of confidence $\alpha = 0.05$.

The results of the Chi Square Test statistical analysis by looking at the value of the Fisher Exact Test about the relationship of the Development of RS SIM based on Knowledge Management based on Knowledge Creation on Employee Performance at RSUP DR. Wahidin Sudirohusodo Makassar obtained the value of $\rho (0,000) < \alpha (0.05)$. This shows that there is a relationship between the Development of RS SIM based on Knowledge

Management based on Knowledge Creation on Employee Performance at RSUP DR. Wahidin Sudirohusodo Makassar in 2014.

The results of the Chi Square Test statistical analysis by looking at the value of the Fisher Exact Test about the relationship of the Development of a Knowledge Management-based RS SIM based on Knowledge Storage on Employee Performance at RSUP DR. Wahidin Sudirohusodo Makassar obtained the value of $\rho (0,000) < \alpha (0.05)$. This shows that there is a relationship between the Development of Knowledge Management RS SIM based on Knowledge Storage on Employee Performance at RSUP DR. Wahidin Sudirohusodo Makassar in 2014.

The results of the Chi Square Test statistical analysis by looking at the value of the Fisher Exact Test about the relationship of the Development of RS SIM based on Knowledge Management based on Knowledge Transfer to Employee Performance at RSUP DR. Wahidin Sudirohusodo Makassar obtained the value of $\rho (0,000) < \alpha (0.05)$. This shows that there is a relationship between the Development of a Knowledge Management-based RS SIM based on Knowledge Transfer to RSUP DR. Wahidin Sudirohusodo Makassar in 2014.

The results of the Chi Square Test statistical analysis by looking at the value of the Fisher Exact Test about the relationship of the Development of RS Management based on Knowledge Management based on Knowledge Application on Employee Performance at RSUP DR. Wahidin Sudirohusodo Makassar obtained the value of $\rho (0,000) < \alpha (0.05)$. This shows that there is a relationship between the Development of a Knowledge Management-based RS SIM based on Knowledge Application to the Employee Performance of RSUP DR. Wahidin Sudirohusodo Makassar in 2014.

The results of the Chi Square Test statistical analysis by looking at the value of the Fisher Exact Test about the relationship between the Development of Knowledge Management-based RS SIM to RSUP DR.

Wahidin Sudirohusodo Makassar obtained the value of ρ (0,000) $< \alpha$ (0.05). This shows that there is a relationship between the Development of Knowledge Management-based RS SIM on the Employee Performance of RSUP DR. Wahidin Sudirohusodo Makassar in 2014.

Multivariate analysis was carried out to determine the Knowledge Management Development RS-based variables that influence the Employee Performance of RSUP DR. Wahidin Sudirohusodo Makassar In 2014 used Multiple Regression Analysis. The probability value obtained is less than p (0,000) $< \alpha$ (0.05), which means that the overall variable is the Development of Knowledge Management-based RS SIM consisting of Knowledge Creation, Knowledge Storage / Retrieval, Knowledge Transfer and Knowledge Application, together (simultaneously) affect the Employee Performance of RSUP DR. Wahidin Sudirohusodo.

The partial test results (t-test) show that the Knowledge Creation variable has a value of ρ (0.063) $> \alpha$ (0.05) which means that the Development of a Hospital SIM based on Knowledge Management based on Knowledge Creation does not affect the Employee Performance of RSUP DR. Wahidin Sudirohusodo Makassar partially. The Knowledge Storage / Retrieval variable Partial test result (t-test) shows the value of ρ (0,332) $> \alpha$ (0,05) which means that the Development of RS MIS based on Knowledge Management based on Knowledge Storage / Retrieval does not affect RSUP DR. Wahidin Sudirohusodo Makassar partially.

The results of the partial test (t-test) Knowledge Transfer variable shows the value of ρ (0.024) $< \alpha$ (0.05) which means the Development of an RS SIM based on Knowledge Management based on Knowledge Transfer has an effect on the Employee Performance of RSUP DR. Wahidin Sudirohusodo Makassar partially. Partial test results (t-test) Knowledge Application variables show the value of ρ (0.013) $< \alpha$ (0.05) which means the

Development of RS MIS based on Knowledge Management based on Knowledge Application has an effect on the Employee Performance of RSUP DR. Wahidin Sudirohusodo Makassar partially. The next analysis is the determination coefficient test obtained $R^2 = 0.495$ which can be interpreted that 49.5% of RSUP DR. Wahidin Sudirohusodo Makassar is influenced by the Development of an RS SIM based on Knowledge Management which consists of Knowledge Creation, Knowledge Storage / Retrieval, Knowledge Transfer and Knowledge Application while 50.5% can be influenced by other factors.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the research that has been done, it can be concluded that there is a relationship between the Development of Knowledge Management-based RS SIM on the Performance of RSUP DR. Wahidin Sudirohusodo Makassar in 2014, Development of Knowledge Management-based RS SIM has an effect on RS Employee Performance, From the 4 variables of Knowledge Management Based on SIM SIM, only 2 have partial influence, namely Knowledge Transfer and Knowledge Application. It is expected that the Director of RSUP DR Wahidin Sudirohusodo Makassar to make the results of this study as a continuous step of improvement to improve the RS information system, this research can be used as basic data for further research related to improving employee performance and Hospital Information Systems.

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